

Can LLMs Judge Argument Quality?

Evaluating Large Language Models on Argument Convincingness Ranking

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1 Project Overview

We study argument quality in a pairwise formulation: given a debate topic and two arguments A and B, predict which is more convincing. Pairwise argument ranking has been studied using crowdsourced datasets and encoder models [2], but prior work does not systematically evaluate cross-topic generalization or compare against modern LLMs. We compare fine-tuned RoBERTa-base (three progressive versions) against zero-shot and 3-shot prompting of GPT-5.5, Llama3 8B, and Mistral 7B, evaluating on both in-domain and cross-topic test sets.

Key findings: (1) RoBERTa v3 matches GPT-5.5 zero-shot (65.7% vs 66.5%) using a model 50× smaller; (2) progressive regularization eliminates the cross-topic generalization gap (from 3.0 to 0.0 points); (3) few-shot prompting helps weak models but introduces severe position bias in Mistral; (4) all models converge near 50% on hard pairs, revealing a task-level ambiguity ceiling driven by annotation noise rather than model failure.

2 Approaches

2.1 Fine-tuned RoBERTa

RoBERTa-base [3] is an encoder-only transformer (125M parameters) pre-trained with masked language modeling on 160GB of text. Its bidirectional self-attention is well-suited for pairwise comparison: given input [CLS] topic [SEP] arg_a [SEP] arg_b, every token in argument A attends to every token in argument B across all 12 layers, producing a joint representation in the [CLS] embedding. A linear classification head maps this 768-dimensional vector to a binary prediction (A wins / B wins). We train three progressive versions:

v1 (baseline): Standard fine-tuning with AdamW, LR=1e-5, batch size 16, gradient clipping at 1.0, linear warmup over 10% of training steps, 6 epochs, validation-based checkpoint saving.

v2 (generalization improvements): Five additions over v1: (i) topic prepended to input so the model knows the debate context; (ii) pair-flipping augmentation where every (A, B, label=A) pair generates a (B, A, label=B) pair, doubling training data and removing ordering artifacts; (iii) label smoothing ($\alpha = 0.1$) to prevent overconfident predictions; (iv) layerwise LR decay (factor 0.9) so lower layers are updated more conservatively, preserving pre-trained representations; (v) freeze bottom 6 layers to force the model to rely on general language understanding rather than task-specific pattern memorization.

v3 (ranking loss and test-time debiasing): Replaces cross-entropy with margin ranking loss (margin=0.3). Instead of classifying A or B, the model learns that the winner’s logit score must exceed the loser’s by at least 0.3 units, directly encoding the ranking nature of the task. Additionally, test-time pair flipping averages predictions over (A,B) and (B,A) orderings, eliminating any residual position bias at inference time. V3 is trained for 12 epochs using a decayed LR ($5e-6$ for the continuation phase).

2.2 LLM Prompting

We evaluate GPT-5.5 (OpenAI API), Llama3 8B, and Mistral 7B (Ollama, 4-bit quantized) in zero-shot and 3-shot settings. The system prompt instructs the model to judge clarity, relevance, logical soundness, and persuasiveness:

System: You are an expert debate judge evaluating argument quality. Given a topic and two arguments (A and B), decide which argument is of higher quality. Consider clarity, relevance, logical soundness, and persuasiveness. Reply with ONLY the single letter “A” or “B”.

For 3-shot prompting, we prepend three labeled examples sampled from easy training pairs (score diff > 0.20), following the chat format: user turn (topic + arguments), assistant turn (correct label). Easy examples are chosen deliberately so the model learns the concept of quality rather than memorizing difficult edge cases. We also collect confidence scores (0–100) from GPT-5.5 by modifying the prompt to output JSON: {"choice": "A", "confidence": 72}.

3 Experimental Setup

3.1 Models

RoBERTa-base [3]: 12-layer transformer encoder, 125M parameters, pre-trained on 160GB of text with masked language modeling. 3 versions (v1, v2 and v3). All experiments use a fixed random seed (42) for reproducibility.

GPT-5.5: Accessed via OpenAI API over HTTPS with 512 max completion tokens. Zero-shot and 3-shot configurations evaluated.

Llama3 8B and **Mistral 7B**: Run locally via Ollama using 4-bit quantized GGUF format on an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1660 Ti (6GB VRAM). Zero-shot and 3-shot configurations evaluated.

3.2 Dataset

Dataset: IBM ArgQ corpus [1]: 30,000 crowd-sourced arguments across 71 topics with Weighted Average quality scores. We construct pairwise comparisons with a 60/11 train/held-out topic split. Pairs are bucketed by score difference: **easy** ($\Delta > 0.20$), **medium** ($0.10 < \Delta \leq 0.20$), **hard** ($\Delta \leq 0.10$).

Split	Topics	Pairs
Train	60	3,587
In-domain test	60	897
Cross-topic test	11	819

Table 1: Dataset splits.

3.3 Evaluation Metrics

We report four metrics. **Pairwise accuracy** $\frac{|{i:\hat{y}_i=y_i}|}{N}$ is our primary metric. **F1 score** is the harmonic mean of precision and recall for class B. **Precision and recall** are reported per class to detect label preference. **Spearman** ρ measures rank correlation between confidence scores and ground-truth score differences.

4 Results

Table 2 presents the main results. RoBERTa v3 achieves 65.7% in-domain accuracy, only 0.8 points behind GPT-5.5 zero-shot (66.5%), while using a model 50× smaller. Crucially, v3 achieves identical in-domain and cross-topic accuracy (65.7%), the only model in our experiment with a zero generalization gap. Among LLMs, GPT-5.5 is the clear leader, followed by Llama3 3-shot and Mistral zero-shot. Llama3 zero-shot at 53.5% is barely above random (50%), suggesting the model has minimal internal model of argument quality without examples.

Notably, v3’s recall (0.616) is substantially higher than v1 (0.534) and v2 (0.514), reflecting that test-time pair flipping corrects the B-prediction bias present in both earlier models. The Spearman correlation between model margin scores and ground-truth score difference confirms that v3 is the best calibrated RoBERTa variant: $\rho = 0.190$ in-domain and $\rho = 0.128$ cross-topic, both statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), compared to v1’s $\rho = 0.097$ and v2’s $\rho = 0.175$.

Model	In-dom.	Cross	Drop	F1	Prec.	Rec.
RoBERTa v1	64.3	61.3	-3.0	0.601	0.687	0.534
RoBERTa v2	63.7	62.8	-0.9	0.587	0.684	0.514
RoBERTa v3	65.7	65.7	0.0	0.644	0.673	0.616
GPT-5.5 (0-shot)	66.5	65.9	-0.6	0.667	0.660	0.664
GPT-5.5 (3-shot)	65.6	–	-0.9	0.660	0.656	0.664
Llama3 (0-shot)	53.5	54.9	+1.4	0.578	0.532	0.632
Llama3 (3-shot)	62.1	–	+8.6	0.621	0.623	0.618
Mistral (0-shot)	60.1	61.0	+0.9	0.628	0.590	0.672
Mistral (3-shot)	58.0	–	-2.1	0.430	0.679	0.315

Table 2: Main results. Drop = cross minus in-domain for RoBERTa; 3-shot minus 0-shot for LLMs.

Model	Overall	Easy	Medium	Hard
RoBERTa v1	64.3	73.6	60.3	53.6
RoBERTa v3	65.7	76.8	59.9	53.6
GPT-5.5 (0-shot)	66.5	79.1	62.4	50.2
Llama3 (3-shot)	62.1	72.5	59.0	48.4
Mistral (0-shot)	60.1	67.1	55.2	54.0

Table 3: Accuracy (%) by difficulty on in-domain test set.

5 Analysis and Discussion

5.1 Failure Mode 1: Hard Pairs as a Task Ceiling

Hypothesis: Hard pairs (score diff ≤ 0.10) are genuinely ambiguous rather than a model failure.

All models, including GPT-5.5, converge near 50% on hard pairs (Table 3). A score difference of 0.05 between two arguments reflects near-identical crowd-sourced ratings. When human annotators disagree at this level, the signal in the ground truth label is essentially noise, and model performs no better than random choice.

Example: Topic: “We should ban factory farming.” Arg A scores 0.512, Arg B scores 0.503 (diff = 0.009). Both make similar points about animal welfare with similar specificity. Predicting A over B is equivalent to guessing.

5.2 Failure Mode 2: Few-Shot Position Bias in Mistral

Hypothesis: Few-shot examples can introduce systematic position bias, causing models to prefer argument A regardless of content.

Mistral 3-shot predicted A in 687/896 pairs (76.7%), despite a near-balanced label distribution (445 A, 451 B). Precision for B was 0.679 (when it predicted B, it

was usually right) but recall was only 0.315 (it missed 69% of actual B cases). F1 dropped from 0.628 to 0.430. Mistral learned the spurious pattern “pick A” from the few-shot label distribution rather than quality signals. GPT-5.5 is robust to this artifact, suggesting stronger models are less susceptible to prompt-induced biases.

Verification: Swapping A and B in Mistral’s few-shot examples would shift bias toward B, a directly testable debiasing check.

5.3 Failure Mode 3: Topic Overfitting in RoBERTa v1

Hypothesis: RoBERTa v1’s 3-point cross-topic drop reflects topic-specific pattern memorization.

RoBERTa v1 drops 3.0 points on cross-topic while GPT-5.5 drops only 0.6 points. Layer freezing and LLRD in v2/v3 preserve general language representations, reducing this gap to 0.9 and 0.0 points respectively. This confirms early fine-tuning layers were adapting to topic-specific vocabulary rather than general quality signals. V3, with frozen lower layers, maintains consistent accuracy across both training and held-out topics.

5.4 Position Bias and Score Difference Analysis

(a) A vs B prediction proportions. Mistral 3-shot predicts A 76.7% of the time. Llama3 and Mistral zero-shot show a B-preference bias, possibly from recency effects in pretraining.

(b) Accuracy vs score difference bin. GPT-5.5 reaches 95.4% on the easiest pairs. Llama3 plateaus near 57% regardless of difficulty, indicating no meaningful internal quality model.

Figure 1: Position bias (left) and score difference threshold analysis (right).

Three patterns emerge from the score difference analysis: (1) all models fall below 50% for score diff < 0.05 – these pairs are effectively noise; (2) RoBERTa v3 and GPT-5.5 scale similarly across difficulty bins; (3) Llama3 shows almost no improvement with increasing score difference, confirming it is essentially guessing regardless of pair difficulty.

5.5 Linguistic Feature Analysis

Correct predictions have higher score_diff than incorrect ones across all models (mean correct: 0.245, mean incorrect: 0.174, Mann-Whitney $p < 0.001$), confirming model accuracy is driven by pair difficulty. Argument length shows a weak

positive correlation with quality (longer wins in 56.5% of pairs) – a real signal rather than a bias, but insufficient on its own to explain model behavior. Evidence word counts (“because”, “therefore”, “research”) show no meaningful correlation with correctness ($p > 0.05$), indicating surface proxies cannot substitute for semantic quality judgment.

Figure 2: **Left: longer-is-winner rates by model:** models get it right when the longer argument is the winner, confirming length is a real quality signal. **Right: mean score gap for correct vs incorrect predictions:** all models struggle when the quality difference is small.

6 Limitations and Future Work

Dataset size and diversity. Training on 3,587 pairs across 60 topics is relatively limited. Larger and more diverse datasets would allow more reliable estimates of cross-topic generalization and reduce sensitivity to topic-specific patterns.

LLM versions. Llama3 8B and Mistral 7B represent mid-2024 model releases. Newer versions (Llama 3.2, Mistral Small 3.1) would likely score higher, particularly on few-shot tasks.

Future directions. Promising extensions include: (1) DeBERTa-v3-base as a drop-in replacement for RoBERTa, with consistently stronger classification performance; (2) mixed precision (FP16) training to reduce compute cost; (3) hard-pair oversampling to improve accuracy on the most ambiguous pairs; (4) multi-task learning combining quality ranking with difficulty prediction.

7 Code and Demo

Code: <https://github.com/Sambhav101/Argument-Quality-Ranking>
 Models: HF/roberta-v2, HF/roberta-v3

Key scripts: `build_pairs.py` (data), `train_roberta{, _v2, _v3}.py` (training), `evaluate_roberta{, _v2, _v3}.py` (evaluation), `eval_llm.py`

(LLM baselines), `linguistic_analysis.py` (analysis), `plot_results.py` / `plot_analysis.py` (figures). Requirements: Python 3.8+, PyTorch 2.3.0, Transformers 4.41.0, Ollama, CUDA 12.x.

8 Learning Outcomes

This project shifted several preconceptions. I assumed fine-tuned task-specific models would substantially outperform zero-shot LLMs; however, the result (65.7% vs 66.5%) is much closer than expected, suggesting that frontier LLMs have acquired stronger implicit task knowledge than commonly assumed, even without labeled supervision.

I also assumed few-shot prompting would uniformly improve performance. Mistral’s F1 collapse from 0.628 to 0.430 was surprising and highlighted how position bias can emerge from seemingly benign prompt choices. The design of few-shot examples matters as much as the examples themselves.

Another important methodological lesson I learned is that accuracy alone is misleading. Mistral 3-shot’s 58% accuracy looks acceptable until you see the F1 and recall breakdown revealing near-total label bias. Reporting multiple metrics (especially per-class precision and recall) is essential for understanding model behavior on imbalanced or biased prediction tasks.

9 Contributions

This project was completed individually by Sambhav Shrestha. All code, experiments, and analysis were performed by the author.

References

- [1] Shai Gretz, Roni Friedman, Edo Cohen-Karlik, Assaf Toledo, Dan Lahav, Ranit Aharonov, and Noam Slonim. 2020. A large-scale dataset for argument quality ranking: Construction and analysis. In *Proceedings of AAAI 2020*.
- [2] Ivan Habernal and Iryna Gurevych. 2016. Which argument is more convincing? analyzing and predicting convincingness of web arguments using bidirectional lstm. In *Proceedings of ACL 2016*.
- [3] Yinhan Liu, Myle Ott, Naman Goyal, Jingfei Du, Mandar Joshi, Danqi Chen, Omer Levy, Mike Lewis, Luke Zettlemoyer, and Veselin Stoyanov. 2019. RoBERTa: A robustly optimized BERT pretraining approach. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.11692*.

A Additional Figures

Figure 3: Overall accuracy for all models. The dotted line marks GPT-5.5 zero-shot as the frontier LLM baseline. RoBERTa v3 is the closest fine-tuned model at 0.8 points behind.

Figure 4: Accuracy by difficulty level. All models converge near chance on hard pairs regardless of model size or training approach, confirming a task-level annotation ceiling.

Figure 5: Training curves for RoBERTa v1, v2, and v3 across epochs. V3's margin ranking loss sustains improvement through 12 epochs.

Figure 6: Train vs validation accuracy per model version. V3 maintains the tightest gap, indicating better regularization.